

Herbal Combination Interactive Effects on Glycaemic and Lipid Profile of Diabetes

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Abstract:- Diabetes has an impact on organs and is treatable using herbs. The research aims at treating diabetes through a multifunctional targeted approach using an herbal mixture extract. Three herbs with well-documented potent antidiabetic properties were employed – groundnut husk, Moringa leaves, and garden egg leaves. The pulverized extracts were preliminarily tested for their phytochemicals by standard method. Wistar rats (25) were randomly allocated as five rats into five mental cages in Groups 1 to 5. Groups 2 to 5 were streptozotocin-induced for three consecutive days. Group 1 (normal untreated) and 5 (diabetic untreated) received distilled water (5ml/kg), and Groups 2 to 4 received equal herbal mixtures at 100, 200, and 300 mg/kg body weight, in that order for three weeks. Serum lipid and glucose concentrations determined were on 10hrs fasted rats. Furthermore, a four-week no-treatment period was extended, with glucose monitored. The extracts contain many phytochemicals. The lipid and glucose concentrations were significant from the diabetic untreated ($P < 0.05$), except in High-density cholesterol. The best improvement in serum glucose concentration was (4.37 mol/l: 61.00%) and lipid profile (108.00mg/dl for Total cholesterol, 120.88mg/dl for Triglyceride), Group-4 and 38.02mg/dl for High-density lipoprotein cholesterol, Group-2. The percentage reduction in glucose concentrations of the extended four-week no-treated were 49.31%, 56.20%, and 68.20% for groups 2, 3, and 4. The results indicated glucose lowering and favorable lipid status of extracts. There were stable glucose concentrations in the extended four weeks, with no treatment. It may have resulted from a synergetic effect than individual plants through multiple targets.

Keywords: Herbs, Diabetes, multiple targets, glucose concentration and lipid profile.

Email: tilong3788@yahoo.com

Received: May 26, 2023

Revised: August 20, 2023

Accepted: September 18, 2023

About the Journal: SJANS is a multidisciplinary science journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Science, Nigeria Police Academy, Kano, Nigeria

1.0 Introduction

Herbal mixture is a core part of all traditional medicine (Schmidt *et al.*, 2008, Conboy *et al.*, 2007, and Xutian *et al.*, 2009). They are starting materials for drug manufacture and, by extension, pharmacologically active compounds (Li and Vederas, 2009). Richly are herbs in secondary metabolites (Hartmann, 2007 and Jenke-Kodama *et al.*, 2008). These metabolites have antidiabetic properties (Afrisham *et al.*, 2015) and are effective in health restoration due to the multiplier effects of protracted high glucose concentrations in the body. Herbs' therapeutic potential is the window opportunity for the treatment or prevention of diseases. These diseases are diabetes and others (Russo *et al.*, 2015).

Diabetes is the third-ranked killer of human beings after cancer and cardiovascular disease (Li *et al.*, 2004). The most chronic illness of disease is Diabetes (Silva *et al.*, 2018). Considering the prevalence, the negative impact on the quality of life of suffers via economic and

social effects. Currently, many individuals worldwide are affected by diabetes. In the past three decades, despite the progress made in diabetes, the results are still far from expectations. The treatments target lowering blood sugar levels. This lowering of sugar levels only to treat diabetes is not all-inclusive. Hence, the exertion by many that treatment will help, but the disease will progress. It is the shortfall in the non-herb treatment approach. This treatment is not holistic. However, the logic in herbal combination is a holistic approach, emphasizing health rather than the disease (diabetes as in this case). The attention is on the individual rather than the ailment afflicting the patient. Diabetes has its signature in many organs (Figure 1). It posited diabetes as a disease for a holistic approach. The researcher claims that an herbal mixture is a holistic and matchless treatment approach to diabetes and others. It might be part of the reason why it is a core part of all systems of traditional medicine practices. Western medicine has clued herbs in drug formulation.

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Today, many treatments with medicinal plants for disease management are recommended (Kooti *et al.*, 2015 and Badgajar *et al.*, 2014), and diabetes is a case in point. Diabetes requires a whole different approach, as the disease signature is in all organs (Figure 1), there is need for a synergistic approach at multiple targets. Since this disorder is a manifold derangement, herbs and their synergistic combination are fulfilling for the successful treatment of diabetes. The research aims to treat the disease with an herbal mixture that has a multifunctional targeted approach. Three herbs with well-documented potent antidiabetic properties were employed – groundnut husk (Tsujita *et al.*, 2014, 1990, Paolisso *et al.*, 1990, Sjogren *et al.*, 1988, and Resnick, 1993) and *Moringa* leaves (Adisakwattana and Chanathong, 2011, Ndong *et al.*, 2007, Jaiswal *et al.*, 2009 and Botta *et al.*, 2018 and Gupta *et al.*, 12) and garden egg leaves (Okafor *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 1: Signature of diabetes in various organs (<https://qph.cf2.quoracdn.net/main-qimg-7844bd17336ad88252b0e381a4e754b4>)

2.0 Material and Method

2.1 Herbal preparation

The fresh groundnut husk, *Moringa* leaves, and garden egg leaves (Figure 2-4) were from different locations at Abuja and dried under shade for two weeks. The plant material pulverization is by mortar and pestle. Six hundred grams of each finely pulverized plant material were soaked in distilled water at 50ml to 3g for 24 hours. The filtrates from each herb

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

were mixed and stirred vigorously in a magnetic stirrer for an hour. The extract mixture drying was under vacuum until constant weight and kept as the crude water extract. The dried pulverized extract was re-constituted with water in a ratio of 1:2 weight by volume.

Figure 2: *Moringa* leaves

Figure 3: Groundnut husk

Figure 4: Garden egg leaves

2.2 Animal

Inbred Wistar rats, healthy and of all sexes, weighing between 120 and 160 g, were employed for this research. The Wistar rats (25) were divided into five groups of five rats each and randomly allocated to five mental cages as Group 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5. Groups 2 to 5 were streptozotocin-induced for three consecutive days. Diabetes is 10.60 ± 0.70 mmol/L of plasma glucose concentration. Group 1 (Normal untreated) and 5 (Diabetic untreated) received only distilled water (5ml/kg). Groups 3 to 4 were

given equal herbal mixtures at 100, 200, and 300 mg/kg body weight. The treated group was left for weeks (4) of non-treatment extension. The rats fasted for 10 hours in each glucose and lipid profile measurement.

2.3 Assay of Biochemical parameters

Each glucose concentration estimation was by glucometer (Trinder, 1969), and the lipid profile concentration: Triglycerides by McGowan *et al.* (1983), Total Cholesterol by Allain *et al.* (1974) and High-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol by modified Lopes-Virella *et al.* (1977).

Preliminary qualitative phytochemical analysis of the individual extracts in the mixture was using the standard method of Harborne (1973).

3.0 Statistical Analysis

The statistical product and service solution (SPSS) was for statistical data analyses of the mean and standard deviation of the five rats. The percentage calculation was from the mean of the data generated. Post hoc analyses were at a statistical difference of $P < 0.05$. All percentages calculations were from the diabetic untreated.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Results

The results are in Tables 1, 2, 3, and 4. The data generated were, in mean and percentage, and the non-parametric as – and +. In Table 1, the glucose concentration has a patterned increase among the treated (Group 2 through 4), and the decreased changes in concentrations were inversely proportional to the amount of extract administered. The glucose concentration was lowest in group 4 (4.37 mmol/l), with a percentage change of 61.00 as calculated from group 5- Diabetic untreated (positive control). The highest concentration was 6.09 mmol/l in group- 2, with a percentage change of 45.61 % as calculated from group-5 (Diabetic untreated). The changes in glucose concentration were significant, with the positive control at $p < 0.05$ in all the treated groups. The positive control glucose concentration was (11.20 mmol/l), and the untreated group-1(negative control) glucose concentration was 3.90 mmol/l, with 65.20 % as calculated from the positive control. In the negative control group, glucose concentration was significant with the positive group glucose concentration.

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

Table 1: Serum glucose levels of wistar rats after administration herbal mixtures

Group	Glucose concentrations in mmo/l	Percentage change in concentration
Group 1	3.90±1.93*	65.20
Group 2	6.09±1.41*	45.61
Group 3	5.25±5.52*	53.10
Group 4	4.37±2.01*	61.00
Group 5	11.20±3.87	Base line

Values bearing * is significant at P<0.05.

Table 2: Percentage change in glucose levels following extended period of non-treatment

Group	Glucose concentration (mmol/l)	Percentage Change
Group 2	5.68*	49.31
Group 3	4.91*	56.20
Group 4	4.12*	63.20

Values bearing * is significant at P<0.05

Table 3: Lipid profile of treated rats in the extended period of non-treatment (mg/dl)

Group	T- CHO	TAG	HDL-CHO
Group1	102.32 ±22.30*	87.44 ±7.82*	36.04 ±1.24
Group 2	125.53 ±12.08*	141.97 ±6.23*	33.02 ±3.21
Group 3	112.23 ±13.07*	133.67 ±3.23*	37.22 ±4.32
Group 4	108.00 ±7.32*	120.88 ±27.91*	42.91 ±5.20
Group 5	141.32 ±5.04	160.64 ±63.52	34.60 ±6.54

Values bearing * is significant at P<0.05

T- CHO=Total cholesterol, TAG=Triglyceride, HDL-CHO=High-density lipoprotein cholesterol.

Table 4: Phytochemicals in the herbal extracts

Phytochemical	Moringa leaves	groundnut husk	garden egg leaves
Alkaloids,	+	-	+
Saponins,	+	-	+
Tannins	+	-	+
Steroids	+	-	-
Phenolic acids	+	-	-

Glucosinolates,	+	-	-
Flavonoids	+	+	+
Terpenes	+	-	-
Phenol	-	+	+
Diterpenes	-	+	-
Terpenoid	-	+	+
Carbohydrate	-	+	-
Anthroquinones	-	-	+

Values bearing (+) is present in the extract and values bearing (-) is absent in the extract.

Table 2 of the extended period of none treatment for groups 2 through 4 has a glucose concentration of 5.68 mmol/l, with the percentage change (49.31 %) as calculated from positive control for group-2, 4.91 mmol/l with the percentage change (56.20 %) as calculated from positive control for group-3 and 4.12 mmol/l with the percentage change (63.20 %) as calculated from positive control for group 3. They depicted patterned changes in glucose concentration. They were all significantly different from the positive control. The most favourable change in glucose concentration and percentage was in group 4.

Table 3 on the lipid profile contains Total Cholesterol (T- CHO), Triglyceride (TAG), and High-Density Lipoprotein (HDL-CHO) in mg/dl. The treated category of groups 2 through 4 exhibited patterned changes in lipid profile concentrations for individual groups. The T-CHO concentrations were 102.32, 125.53, 112.23, 108.00, and 141.32 in Groups 1 through 5. In the treated group (2 through 4), there was a decrease in concentration from groups 2 through 4. The decreased changes in the group were inversely proportional to the extract amount, with group 4 as the highest change from group 5. The groups were significantly different from the positive control at p<0.05. TAG concentration was 87.44, 141.97, 133.67, 120.88, and 160.64 in the same order from groups 1 through 5. In the treated group (groups 2 through 4), there was a decrease in concentration from groups 2 through 4. The decreased changes in the group were inversely proportional to the extract amount, with group 4 as the highest decrease from group 5. The groups were significantly different from the positive control at p<0.05. The HDL-CHO concentration was 36.04, 33.02, 37.22, 42.91, and 34.60 in Groups 1 through 5. In the treated groups (2 through 4), there was a decrease in concentration from groups 4 through 2. The

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decreased changes were directly proportional to the extract amount, with group 4 as the lowest decrease from group 5. There was no significant difference in HDL-CHO concentration for all groups compared with positive control at $p > 0.05$.

Table 4 showed the presence of, at least the following phytochemicals in the extract mixture; alkaloids, saponins, Tannins, Steroids, Phenolic acids, Glucosinolates, Flavonoids, Flavonoids, Terpenes, Phenol, Diterpenes, Terpenoid, Carbohydrate and Anthroquinones.

4.2 Discussion

Many reviewers have described the importance of natural compounds in herbal extracts for the treatment of diseases in human (Butler, 2004, Newman and Cragg, 2007 and Lam, 2007). The continuing and overwhelming contribution (herbs) to expand anti-diabetic agents is evident. As in the present research, the combined herbal mixture with various photochemical compounds derived from the whole crude extract of the three herbs is a holistic therapeutic approach. The potential of the therapeutic effects due to the synergy achieved by the multiple ingredients on different targets is the research strength and expectation of the improved quality of life.

Unlike the single chemical entity focused on a specific single target, the herbal extract and compound in the three herbs (Table 4) represent integrated effects of multi-components upon multi-target sites and dynamic adjustments that will restore the balance of an imbalance caused by diabetes. Li *et al.* (2006, 2008) made the same observation. Because diabetes is multifaceted, a multidimensional approach is worthwhile the herbal combination. Phytochemical analyses (Table 4) proved extracts contain ingredients worth using the plant mixture on diabetic animals. The potential of the individual herbs in the extract mixtures is recognized elsewhere (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2019, Rhaigón *et al.*, 2008, Gramazio *et al.*, 2014, Polepalli *et al.*, 2018, Gonzalez and Salas-Salvado 2006, Francisco, 2008, Arya *et al.*, 2016 and Paddon-Jones *et al.*, 2008).

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

Therefore, it is now essential to explore the potential offered by herbal combinations through integrated approaches toward diabetes, as seen in this research. The percentage reduction in glucose concentrations during the extended four-week of non-treatment and before the extension period was significant in all treated (Table 3). The significance observed in the extended week of the no-treated period indicated the restoration potential of the herbal mixture. Some ingredients may synergistically mimic the mechanisms of the interplays seen in normal glucose haemostasis. Many inter players are involved in glucose haemostasis- hormones, organs, minerals, others. There is the possibility that phytochemicals in the mixture aided in the interplays. Though, the mechanisms, and the contributions of other entities (in the extract mixture), were not investigated. The contributions of the fibre, elements, and others, cannot be ruled out. This finding may prompt that diabetes could be reversible, against popular belief. On this, more investigation is paramount for the validation of research exertion. The extended non-treated period of normalized glucose levels may have resulted from whole herbs having much more effectiveness than its part. The expectation is that it was through multiple targets.

Furthermore, the Total -CHO, TAG, and HDL are lipid components altered in diabetes (Amini and Parvaresh, 2009 and Bhowmik *et al.*, 2018). Similar alterations were observed, in the diabetic-untreated, called positive control (Table 3), in group 5. The treatment caused improvement in the various components of lipids (Table 3). The T-CHO and TAG usually increased the consequence of diabetes (Howard 1987), but HDL-Cholesterol reduced similarly (Taskinen *et al.*, 1992). The reduction in TAG, T-CHO, and concomitant increment in HDL-Cholesterol show normalization in the metabolic syndrome due to diabetes (Nilsson *et al.*, 19). It agreed with previous research by Gadi and Samaha (2007).

Numerous reviews have described the importance of natural compounds in herbal

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

extracts for the treatment of diseases of human (Butler, 2004, Newman and Cragg, 2007, and Lam, 2007). The continuing and overwhelming contribution (herbs) to the expansion of anti-diabetic agents is evident. As in the present research, the combined herbal mixture with various photochemical compounds derived from the whole crude extract of the three herbs is a holistic therapeutic approach. The potential of the therapeutic effects due to the synergy achieved by the multiple ingredients on different targets is the research strength and expectation of the improved quality of life.

5.0 Conclusion

The European Parliament, the US Food and Drug Administration, and the Council proclaimed the approval of herbal mixtures with unknown ingredients if sufficient convincing evidence abode for their safety and efficacy (Silano *et al.*, 2004). The herbal combination in the present study is one such, with little of its phytochemicals determined. With some metabolic disturbance in diabetes verified, and four-week normalized glucose levels in the absence of treatment depict the extract mixture has restored the glucose concentration. The lipid profile improvement is one normalization of attendant consequences.

Most researchers are aware of the complexity of diabetes and oblivious to the reversibility of diabetic states. The results of the researcher projected the possibilities of reversibility. On mature reflection, the researcher feels it is wiser to demonstrate herbal combinations on other metabolic syndromes associated with dysregulated sugar levels.

Conflict of Interest

There was no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgement

The researcher is grateful to Mrs Indubuisi Ngozi for her financial assistance.

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